

Supporting Information for
Specialization predicts population isolation and inbreeding in
grassland associated butterflies

Zachary J. Nolen^{1*}, Isolde van Riemsdijk^{1,2}, Anna Runemark¹

¹ Department of Biology, Lund University, Lund, Sweden

² Section for Hologenomics, Globe Institute, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

*Corresponding author: Zachary J. Nolen

Email: zachary.nolen@biol.lu.se

Supporting Figures and Tables

Figure S1. Sharp drops in N_e in the most recent 4 generations occurring frequently in GONE analyses. Here, trajectories of effective population sizes are depicted as in Figure 3, but with the most recent four generations included. Frequently, the effective population size estimates of the most recent four generations of GONE analyses would differ dramatically from the estimates of the fifth and earlier generations. This was most common in species with consistently very large ($>100\,000$) effective sizes over the past 100 years. Such jumps are consistent with artifacts from small samples sizes or estimating trajectories in populations with genetic substructure (Santiago et al., 2020). However, our population genetic structure analyses did not suggest further genetic substructuring in our datasets. As these were almost always changes in size in a downward direction, we excluded them from the main results to provide more conservative estimates of effective population size.

Aglais urticae

Anthocharis cardamines

Aphantopus hyperantus

Coenonympha pamphilus

Cupido minimus

Cyaniris semiargus

Aglais io

Lycaena phlaes

Maniola jurtina

Ochloides sylvanus

Polyommatus icarus

Figure S2. Admixture results for K 1-4 for the study species. The highest likelihood replicate for each value of K is shown for each species. Bars are individuals, grouped by sample population, colored by probability of membership to one of K clusters. Converged values of K are highlighted in bold within each species, with the highest converged value selected as the 'best fit' estimate of K.

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Figure S3. Correlation of residuals for each species' admixture analyses. For each value of K, we assessed the goodness of fit of our data to that K model of admixture using evalAdmix (Garcia-Erill and Albrechtsen, 2020), visualized here with the pairwise correlation of residuals between individuals (upper left triangle of the matrix) and sampled populations (lower right triangle of the matrix). When individuals/groups of individuals are more similar than the model suggests, they have a positive pairwise correlation, when they are more different, they have a negative. Well-fitting sample pairs have a score of 0.

Figure S4. Individual heterozygosity estimates adjusted for runs of homozygosity. Here, estimates of individual heterozygosity are depicted as boxplots (solid) for sampled populations of each species, colored by the region in Skåne from which the samples came. These estimates were then adjusted by the individual inbreeding coefficient to approximate levels of heterozygosity outside of runs of homozygosity (hashed boxplots, faded). In the specialist species *C. minimus* and *C. semiargus*, much of the variation in heterozygosity is explained by the abundance of runs of homozygosity.

Table S1: Information on butterfly species included in this study. Species were classified into three groups: (1) one of the top five most common species in Sweden in 2020, (2) European Grassland Butterfly Indicator species in the 'Widespread' species grouping of the indicator, and (3) species in the 'Specialist' grouping of the same indicator. Recombination rates are determined from the reference genome, assuming 50cM per chromosome.

Species	Category	Recombination rate (M/bp) ^{***}	GenBank Assembly	Reference Species ^{****}	Reference citation
<i>Aglais io</i>	Common*	4.09E-08	GCA_905147045.1	<i>Aglais io</i>	(Lohse, Mackintosh, et al., 2021)
<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Common*	4.34E-08	GCA_905147175.2	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	(Bishop et al., 2021)
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Common*	3.58E-08	GCA_902806685.2	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	(Mead et al., 2021)
<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Common*/Widespread**	3.71E-08	GCA_905333055.1	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	(Lohse, Weir, et al., 2021)
<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Widespread**	4.34E-08	GCA_905404175.1	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	(Ebdon et al., 2022)
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Widespread**	3.07E-08	GCA_964275175.1	<i>Coenonympha arcania</i>	No genome note
<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Widespread**	2.88E-08	GCA_905333005.2	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	(Lohse, Laetsch, et al., 2021)
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Widespread**	4.08E-08	GCA_905404295.2	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	(Lohse, Hayward, Vila, et al., 2023)
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Widespread**	2.33E-08	GCA_937595015.1	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	(Lohse, Wellcome Sanger Institute Tree of Life programme, et al., 2023)
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Specialist**	2.87E-08	GCA_964277285.1	<i>Cupido argiades</i>	No genome note
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Specialist**	2.76E-08	GCA_905187585.1	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	(Lohse, Hayward, Laetsch, et al., 2023)

* Most common species in Sweden as reported in Pettersson et al., 2022

** European grassland indicator species as reported in van Swaay et al., 2022; divided into 'Widrespread' and 'Specialist' categories

*** Inferred assuming each chromosome is 50cM, then dividing by the total physical length of the autosomes

**** Species where a reference from a related species was used are highlighted in bold

Table S2. Collection, sequencing, and genetic diversity information for samples included in this study. Each sample is a single butterfly individual, grouped by species. Collection coordinates and dates are given. Samples were grouped into sampled 'populations', named under 'Population grouping', which were formed from samples of the same species collected within 15km of each other. These population groupings were subdivided if further genetic substructure was supported by the admixture analyses. All population-level analyses in this study were performed on the groups described in this column. Each population grouping was assigned one of three regions, based on its broad location within Skåne. The percentage of mapping reads and their average sequencing depth in filtered regions of the genome are given as a metric of sequencing quality. Finally, individual estimates of heterozygosity per 1000bp and the inbreeding coefficient estimated from runs of homozygosity > 100kb (*FRoH*) is given.

Sample ID	Species	Region	Population grouping	Collection Date	Latitude	Longitude	Library Prep Method	% Mapped Reads	Mean Filtered Depth	Heterozygosity / 1000bp	Inbreeding Coeff (Froh)
INIO0326	<i>Aglais io</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-25	55.6983	13.4309	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.74	9.4174	6.004	0.00297
INIO0327	<i>Aglais io</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-25	55.6970	13.4311	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.66	10.5163	6.066	0.00286
INIO0332	<i>Aglais io</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-25	55.6971	13.4310	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.68	9.1221	6.195	0.00067
INIO0333	<i>Aglais io</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-25	55.6971	13.4310	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.66	13.414	5.883	0.00224
INIO0369	<i>Aglais io</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-28	55.6975	13.4305	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.71	6.2414	7.394	0.00296
INIO0370	<i>Aglais io</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-28	55.6971	13.4310	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.61	6.6754	6.783	0.00445
INIO0352	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-07-28	55.3881	14.1305	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.69	16.195	5.650	0.00316
INIO0360	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-07-28	55.3858	14.1345	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.55	11.8441	5.922	0.00062
INIO0361	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-07-28	55.3858	14.1345	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.71	8.3094	6.399	0.00311
INIO0364	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-07-28	55.3858	14.1343	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.64	10.3976	5.995	0.00294
INIO0366	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-07-28	55.3859	14.1345	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.68	13.5603	5.804	0.00192
INIO0367	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-07-28	55.3862	14.1345	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.64	10.9749	5.986	0.00118
INIO0288	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southwest	Southwest	2022-07-21	55.3974	12.8643	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.72	12.6246	5.775	0.00678
INIO0298	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southwest	Southwest	2022-07-21	55.3960	12.8712	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.62	6.0038	6.901	0.00087
INIO0338	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southwest	Southwest	2022-07-26	55.3960	12.8712	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.72	9.2004	6.387	0.00037
INIO0339	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southwest	Southwest	2022-07-26	55.3960	12.8712	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.71	8.856	6.487	0.00099
INIO0340	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southwest	Southwest	2022-07-26	55.3962	12.8711	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.69	10.5367	6.110	0.00402
INIO0346	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southwest	Southwest	2022-07-26	55.5231	12.9122	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.63	5.7702	7.673	0.00345
INIO0347	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southwest	Southwest	2022-07-26	55.5231	12.9134	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.47	15.4988	5.667	0.00127
INIO0348	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southwest	Southwest	2022-07-26	55.5230	12.9132	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.66	7.393	6.991	0.00061
INIO0349	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southwest	Southwest	2022-07-26	55.5230	12.9132	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.63	9.4004	6.193	0.00000
INIO0350	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southwest	Southwest	2022-07-26	55.5230	12.9132	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.66	12.0215	5.868	0.00281
INIO0351	<i>Aglais io</i>	Southwest	Southwest	2022-07-26	55.5230	12.9132	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.66	11.7997	6.103	0.00174
H1	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-14	55.7103	13.5176	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.47	10.8897	22.510	0.00030
H2	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-14	55.7103	13.5176	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.46	10.6641	22.424	0.00106
S1	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-21	55.6893	13.4960	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.48	9.8626	22.403	0.00034
S2	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-21	55.6893	13.4960	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.44	9.9131	22.468	0.00000
S3	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-21	55.6893	13.4960	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.44	30.2824	22.879	0.00030
S4	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-21	55.6893	13.4960	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.45	8.4383	22.990	0.00000
S5	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-21	55.6893	13.4960	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.47	9.9675	22.386	0.00035
S7	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-21	55.6893	13.4960	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.45	9.8244	22.473	0.00068
S8	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-21	55.6893	13.4960	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.45	8.649	22.388	0.00103
T1	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-30	55.6979	13.4297	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.46	8.8996	22.392	0.00192
T2	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-30	55.6979	13.4297	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.46	10.254	22.504	0.00095
B1	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-22/07-28	55.3866	14.1295	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.45	9.8199	22.303	0.00000
B2	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-22/07-28	55.3866	14.1295	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.48	10.0205	22.483	0.00089
B3	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-22/07-28	55.3866	14.1295	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.48	10.3449	22.482	0.00000
B4	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-22/07-28	55.3866	14.1295	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.46	12.5604	22.549	0.00067
B5	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-22/07-28	55.3866	14.1295	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.47	11.3971	22.554	0.00085

B6	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-22/07-28	55.3866	14.1295	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.39	9.4756	22.433	0.00071
Y1	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-23/07-22	55.4440	13.9286	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.45	10.1566	22.518	0.00117
Y2	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-23/07-22	55.4440	13.9286	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.47	10.617	22.493	0.00116
Y3	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-23/07-22	55.4440	13.9286	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.47	10.6144	23.219	0.00107
Y4	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-23/07-22	55.4440	13.9286	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.46	10.1532	22.453	0.00070
F1	<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-07-21	55.3960	12.8711	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.43	16.5609	22.807	0.00000
ANCA0007	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-05-26	55.6900	13.4941	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.32	22.1342	19.949	0.01159
ANCA0009	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-05-27	55.6900	13.4942	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.43	15.0786	20.084	0.00227
ANCA0232	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-05-20	55.6965	13.4300	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.4	11.6553	20.236	0.01187
ANCA0233	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-05-20	55.6962	13.4474	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.33	12.6079	18.691	0.06997
ANCA0002	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Southeast	Ystad Golfklubb	2022-05-25	55.4424	13.9337	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.43	19.4053	19.655	0.02240
ANCA0003	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Southeast	Ystad Golfklubb	2022-05-25	55.4424	13.9336	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.31	24.0636	19.978	0.00962
ANCA0004	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Southeast	Ystad Golfklubb	2022-05-25	55.4423	13.9337	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.27	21.5614	19.913	0.01084
ANCA0005	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Southeast	Ystad Golfklubb	2022-05-25	55.4424	13.9336	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.38	14.1792	19.875	0.01398
ANCA0006	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Southeast	Ystad Golfklubb	2022-05-25	55.4450	13.9263	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.31	18.441	19.982	0.00997
APHY0169	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-30	55.6976	13.4299	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.46	7.1562	7.099	0.00383
APHY0175	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-30	55.6960	13.4308	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.5	10.7858	6.371	0.00328
APHY0179	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-30	55.6970	13.4295	Illumina DNA Nextera	97.02	7.6095	7.256	0.00244
APHY0247	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-11	55.6966	13.4317	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.44	8.8423	6.751	0.00465
APHY0249	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-11	55.6962	13.4308	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.87	6.8954	6.904	0.00573
APHY0181	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-07-01	55.5861	14.1568	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.42	4.4119	8.080	0.00292
APHY0182	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-07-01	55.5863	14.1571	Illumina DNA Nextera	97.97	14.0968	6.004	0.01711
APHY0183	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-07-01	55.5863	14.1572	Illumina DNA Nextera	97.21	7.8504	6.784	0.00909
APHY0184	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-07-01	55.5864	14.1571	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.5	10.9134	6.199	0.02807
APHY0185	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-07-01	55.5863	14.1572	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.48	5.3466	8.027	0.01294
APHY0188	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-07-01	55.5860	14.1568	Illumina DNA Nextera	97.43	12.3512	6.175	0.01122
APHY0189	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-07-01	55.5856	14.1569	Illumina DNA Nextera	96.03	10.8123	8.515	0.00196
APHY0154	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-06-29	55.3979	12.8642	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.39	6.3402	7.528	0.01969
APHY0255	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-07-12	55.3974	12.8640	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.47	7.7245	6.949	0.00807
APHY0256	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-07-12	55.3972	12.8641	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.48	7.0168	6.668	0.09214
APHY0257	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-07-12	55.3962	12.8641	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.52	13.4913	5.948	0.04632
APHY0259	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-07-12	55.3970	12.8644	Illumina DNA Nextera	84.24	4.6763	7.411	0.02697
APHY0261	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-07-12	55.3965	12.8656	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.3	12.4425	6.123	0.03447
APHY0262	<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-07-12	55.3973	12.8643	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.33	5.1122	7.170	0.05691
COPA0168	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-30	55.6978	13.4302	Illumina DNA Nextera	72.66	3.3896	15.062	0.00000
COPA0328	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-25	55.6970	13.4311	Illumina DNA Nextera	74.53	4.4075	14.879	0.00000
COPA0024	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-06-16	55.3854	14.1287	Illumina DNA Nextera	73.08	3.6109	14.687	0.00088
COPA0069	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-06-22	55.3887	14.1307	Illumina DNA Nextera	72	5.501	14.762	0.00226
COPA0070	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-06-22	55.3886	14.1307	Illumina DNA Nextera	72.73	7.6889	14.766	0.00030
COPA0071	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-06-22	55.3887	14.1307	Illumina DNA Nextera	71.95	3.0039	14.806	0.00124
COPA0072	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-06-22	55.3889	14.1297	Illumina DNA Nextera	71.89	3.3535	14.581	0.01649
COPA0073	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-06-22	55.3887	14.1307	Illumina DNA Nextera	73.36	7.1189	14.679	0.00056
COPA0074	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2022-06-22	55.3887	14.1307	Illumina DNA Nextera	71.86	4.3073	14.700	0.00145
COPA0139	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-06-29	55.3962	12.8663	Illumina DNA Nextera	74.3	4.0611	14.777	0.00209
COPA0145	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-06-29	55.3963	12.8670	Illumina DNA Nextera	72.67	3.6077	14.348	0.02573
COPA0151	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-06-29	55.3962	12.8657	Illumina DNA Nextera	72.42	3.9525	14.725	0.01521
COPA0153	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-06-29	55.3974	12.8643	Illumina DNA Nextera	72.09	2.4567	15.137	0.00388

COPA0157	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-06-29	55.3955	12.8653	Illumina DNA Nextera	72.17	2.9566	15.114	0.01312
COPA0254	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-07-12	55.3973	12.8642	Illumina DNA Nextera	74.97	5.0577	14.752	0.00213
COPA0264	<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-07-12	55.3972	12.8643	Illumina DNA Nextera	72.4	3.111	15.504	0.00436
CUMI0012	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-14	55.6960	13.4310	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.78	11.9278	8.083	0.08205
CUMI0048	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-21	55.6953	13.4316	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.54	8.3434	9.153	0.01585
CUMI0050	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-21	55.6959	13.4311	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.46	12.0044	8.091	0.09402
CUMI0051	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-21	55.6957	13.4311	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.23	7.516	9.493	0.09579
CUMI0052	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-21	55.6957	13.4311	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.41	9.144	8.268	0.10865
CUMI0178	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-30	55.6957	13.4305	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.75	8.1511	9.389	0.03130
CUMI0104	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-06-27	55.5860	14.1569	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.58	7.224	9.091	0.04148
CUMI0106	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-06-27	55.5860	14.1568	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.55	8.7636	8.811	0.05026
CUMI0108	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-06-27	55.5849	14.1571	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.41	5.6966	9.037	0.06528
CUMI0110	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-06-27	55.5849	14.1571	Illumina DNA Nextera	93.54	9.253	8.751	0.03372
CUMI0111	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-06-27	55.5850	14.1569	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.47	8.6802	9.012	0.02040
CUMI0112	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-06-27	55.5850	14.1571	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.48	4.8347	9.211	0.04569
CUMI0113	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-06-28	55.5862	14.1568	Illumina DNA Nextera	94.66	7.7189	9.277	0.07535
CUMI0043	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-17	55.3786	13.2498	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.43	7.0387	7.863	0.17598
CUMI0044	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-17	55.3786	13.2497	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.52	8.8006	8.011	0.12124
CUMI0045	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-17	55.3787	13.2497	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.29	9.1058	8.269	0.12665
CUMI0047	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-17	55.3783	13.2469	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.41	5.8855	7.110	0.26755
CUMI0127	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-29	55.3783	13.2488	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.52	4.3022	9.244	0.13592
CUMI0130	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-29	55.3784	13.2496	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.51	6.6552	8.270	0.12566
CUMI0132	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-29	55.3784	13.2497	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.72	6.8555	8.026	0.14694
CUMI0026	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Smygehuk	2022-06-17	55.3392	13.3598	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.53	9.8037	6.933	0.24614
CUMI0027	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Smygehuk	2022-06-17	55.3401	13.3605	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.43	7.4942	6.334	0.33745
CUMI0028	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Smygehuk	2022-06-17	55.3401	13.3606	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.5	9.3462	7.381	0.18889
CUMI0029	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Smygehuk	2022-06-17	55.3401	13.3606	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.64	9.9028	8.446	0.07153
CUMI0030	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Smygehuk	2022-06-17	55.3401	13.3606	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.43	4.433	9.540	0.09926
CUMI0034	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Smygehuk	2022-06-17	55.3401	13.3606	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.38	5.6904	7.893	0.23556
CUMI0035	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Southwest	Smygehuk	2022-06-17	55.3401	13.3606	Illumina DNA Nextera	95.61	10.5521	7.005	0.22861
MZLU00107457	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Central	Silvakra	2021-07-04	55.6695	13.4924	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.66	18.5513	7.362	0.06389
MZLU00107460	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Central	Silvakra	2021-07-04	55.6695	13.4924	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.64	15.0004	7.353	0.06131
MZLU00107464	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Central	Silvakra	2021-07-04	55.6695	13.4924	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.55	14.7494	7.587	0.03122
MZLU00107497	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Central	Silvakra	2021-07-04	55.6695	13.4924	Illumina DNA Nextera	94.21	11.2183	7.172	0.07743
MZLU00107498	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Central	Silvakra	2021-07-04	55.6695	13.4924	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.37	11.752	7.498	0.03620
MZLU00107499	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Central	Silvakra	2021-07-04	55.6695	13.4924	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.66	12.3946	6.933	0.11634
MZLU00107500	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Central	Silvakra	2021-07-04	55.6695	13.4924	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.56	9.2683	7.255	0.06750
MZLU00107505	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Central	Silvakra	2021-07-04	55.6695	13.4924	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.13	11.9697	7.459	0.05081
MZLU00107520	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Southeast	Kaseberga	2022-06-23	55.3864	14.1014	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.64	14.1651	5.366	0.32366
MZLU00107522	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Southeast	Kaseberga	2022-06-27	55.3864	14.1014	Illumina DNA Nextera	97.84	11.8547	6.433	0.18863
MZLU00107523	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Southeast	Kaseberga	2022-06-27	55.3864	14.1014	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.22	6.7549	7.084	0.11924
MZLU00107524	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Southeast	Kaseberga	2022-06-27	55.3864	14.1014	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.64	11.8238	6.806	0.14050
MZLU00107525	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Southeast	Kaseberga	2022-06-28	55.3864	14.1014	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.62	10.0443	7.156	0.09010
MZLU00107526	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Southeast	Kaseberga	2022-07-01	55.3864	14.1014	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.48	12.4516	7.318	0.07606
MZLU00107527	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Southeast	Kaseberga	2022-07-01	55.3864	14.1014	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.44	9.943	6.914	0.13279
LYPH0248	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-11	55.6952	13.4313	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.81	12.6652	17.637	0.00000
LYPH0269	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-19	55.6967	13.4314	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.52	8.669	18.582	0.00000

LYPH0280	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-19	55.6950	13.5046	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.72	7.6423	18.556	0.00086
LYPH0329	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-07-25	55.6953	13.4317	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.81	7.8655	18.217	0.00000
LYPH0281	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Southeast	Ales Stenar	2022-07-20	55.3818	14.0571	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.73	7.1083	18.432	0.00053
LYPH0282	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Southeast	Ales Stenar	2022-07-20	55.3818	14.0570	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.68	9.8514	18.111	0.00052
LYPH0283	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Southeast	Ales Stenar	2022-07-20	55.3813	14.0560	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.75	9.6083	18.020	0.00044
LYPH0284	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Southeast	Ales Stenar	2022-07-20	55.3815	14.0555	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.75	7.0966	18.288	0.00035
LYPH0285	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Southeast	Ales Stenar	2022-07-20	55.3815	14.0555	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.6	9.1327	18.405	0.00000
LYPH0286	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Southeast	Ales Stenar	2022-07-20	55.3819	14.0547	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.71	9.8569	18.006	0.00058
LYPH0287	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Southeast	Ales Stenar	2022-07-20	55.3814	14.0561	Illumina DNA Nextera	96	7.5043	17.887	0.02418
LYPH0299	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-07-21	55.3960	12.8712	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.68	5.008	19.000	0.00093
LYPH0345	<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-07-26	55.3960	12.8712	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.8	5.6656	18.848	0.00000
MAJU0049	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-21	55.6961	13.4312	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.71	14.9673	18.795	0.00000
MAJU0159	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-30	55.6975	13.4301	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.72	8.8386	19.500	0.00032
MAJU0160	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-30	55.6978	13.4301	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.67	8.4781	19.533	0.00045
MAJU0162	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-30	55.6980	13.4297	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.74	8.8409	19.292	0.00338
MAJU0163	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-30	55.6981	13.4297	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.64	16.7197	18.715	0.00070
MAJU0165	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Central	Tvedora	2022-06-30	55.6979	13.4296	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.68	5.8321	20.050	0.00068
MAJU0076	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-22	55.3858	14.1262	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.51	7.5419	20.412	0.00080
MAJU0080	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-23	55.3853	14.1020	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.63	8.1441	20.060	0.00803
MAJU0082	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-23	55.4440	13.9284	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.64	7.8547	19.846	0.00626
MAJU0083	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-23	55.4441	13.9283	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.73	7.5098	19.443	0.00162
MAJU0084	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-23	55.4440	13.9286	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.66	6.9639	20.030	0.00692
MAJU0086	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-23	55.4434	13.9284	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.67	5.8499	20.233	0.00132
MAJU0090	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-23	55.4433	13.9278	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.63	11.4801	18.978	0.00329
MAJU0091	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-27	55.3885	14.1308	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.58	8.2466	20.162	0.00257
MAJU0092	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-27	55.3850	14.1282	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.61	8.6529	19.424	0.00268
MAJU0095	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-27	55.3861	14.1020	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.75	5.8226	20.004	0.00505
MAJU0097	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Southeast	2022-06-27	55.3864	14.1013	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.74	4.9846	20.127	0.00138
MAJU0119	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-29	55.3779	13.2471	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.7	5.7019	20.531	0.00182
MAJU0120	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-29	55.3780	13.2486	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.82	12.9961	18.821	0.00029
MAJU0122	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-29	55.3781	13.2487	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.65	2.6285	19.955	0.00029
MAJU0124	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-29	55.3781	13.2487	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.57	6.848	19.712	0.00317
MAJU0125	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-29	55.3783	13.2487	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.79	3.9571	20.047	0.00030
MAJU0128	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southwest	Railyard	2022-06-29	55.3784	13.2492	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.71	7.3605	19.356	0.00827
OCSY0010	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-05	55.6900	13.4941	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.1	11.8175	14.936	0.00596
OCSY0013	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-14	55.6900	13.4942	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.01	8.969	15.912	0.00425
OCSY0053	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-21	55.6903	13.4948	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.12	5.8841	16.455	0.02022
OCSY0056	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-21	55.6895	13.4936	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.03	15.0449	15.321	0.00273
OCSY0066	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Central	Revinge	2022-06-21	55.6692	13.4934	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.1	15.1232	15.254	0.00064
OCSY0105	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-06-27	55.5860	14.1568	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.12	13.6615	15.352	0.00421
OCSY0109	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Southeast	Smedstorp	2022-06-27	55.5850	14.1570	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.08	3.4068	16.323	0.00716
OCSY0141	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-06-29	55.3973	12.8644	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.84	8.3942	14.928	0.01499
OCSY0143	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-06-29	55.3965	12.8656	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.89	7.7261	14.266	0.05630
OCSY0147	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-06-29	55.3973	12.8656	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.12	8.4474	14.784	0.02120
OCSY0149	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-06-29	55.3975	12.8645	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.15	9.8485	15.410	0.03806
OCSY0155	<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2022-06-29	55.3958	12.8648	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.01	8.2224	17.726	0.03053
PI028	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2020-07-22	55.6951	13.4316	Illumina DNA PCR-Free	98.65	20.7302	12.215	0.00197

PI029	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2020-07-22	55.6951	13.4316	Illumina DNA PCR-Free	99.45	16.0449	12.105	0.00183
PI030	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2020-07-22	55.6951	13.4316	Illumina DNA PCR-Free	99.44	26.9547	12.307	0.00072
PI031	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2020-07-22	55.6951	13.4316	Illumina DNA PCR-Free	99.36	24.1988	12.173	0.00801
PI032	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2020-07-22	55.6951	13.4316	Illumina DNA PCR-Free	99.46	28.3288	12.283	0.00036
PI033	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2020-07-22	55.6951	13.4316	Illumina DNA PCR-Free	99.46	22.7542	12.069	0.01501
PI034	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2020-07-22	55.6951	13.4316	Illumina DNA PCR-Free	99.43	23.3546	12.249	0.00178
PI035	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2020-07-22	55.6951	13.4316	Illumina DNA PCR-Free	99.27	25.6924	12.258	0.00026
PI036	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Central	Tvedora	2020-07-22	55.6951	13.4316	Illumina DNA PCR-Free	99.44	21.016	12.179	0.00145
POIC0877	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2021-08-02	55.3866	14.1297	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.26	9.9366	12.195	0.00077
POIC0878	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2021-08-02	55.3866	14.1297	Illumina DNA Nextera	93.41	5.0832	12.688	0.00081
POIC0879	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2021-08-02	55.3866	14.1297	Illumina DNA Nextera	97.51	6.3528	12.365	0.00137
POIC0880	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2021-08-02	55.3866	14.1297	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.41	7.2612	12.379	0.00027
POIC0881	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2021-08-02	55.3866	14.1297	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.43	13.5132	12.208	0.00117
POIC0882	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2021-08-02	55.3866	14.1297	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.48	9.2991	12.365	0.00223
POIC0883	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2021-08-02	55.3866	14.1297	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.5	13.1306	12.218	0.00000
POIC0884	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southeast	Backakra	2021-08-02	55.3866	14.1297	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.08	9.3591	12.267	0.00047
POIC0753	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2021-07-23	55.4025	12.8853	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.38	6.395	12.195	0.01699
POIC0754	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2021-07-23	55.4025	12.8853	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.48	11.4218	12.188	0.00317
POIC0755	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2021-07-23	55.4025	12.8853	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.47	9.6409	12.293	0.00076
POIC0756	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2021-07-23	55.4025	12.8853	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.52	8.6961	11.840	0.03190
POIC0757	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2021-07-23	55.4025	12.8853	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.49	10.072	12.189	0.00340
POIC0758	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2021-07-23	55.4025	12.8853	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.49	11.1298	12.210	0.00048
POIC0759	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2021-07-23	55.4025	12.8853	Illumina DNA Nextera	99.49	10.3308	12.279	0.00253
POIC0760	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Southwest	Falsterbo	2021-07-23	55.4025	12.8853	Illumina DNA Nextera	98.14	9.8855	12.286	0.00194

Table S3. As close relatives can impact population structure analyses, we removed one of each pair of third degree and closer (using a kinship coefficient of 0.0625 as a cutoff) relatives for the admixture analyses. We removed individuals in a fashion that maximized the total number of individuals in the final analysis. Close relatives were only found in *C. semiargus* and *C. minimus*, with a larger number in the latter species. Individuals removed from the admixture analyses are shown in bold and red.

Species	Sample 1	Sample 2	R0	R1	KING	Inferred Relationship
<i>C. semiargus</i>	MZLU00107524	MZLU00107520	0.221668	0.342428	0.118473	HS
<i>C. semiargus</i>	MZLU00107527	MZLU00107526	0.266926	0.295346	0.091063	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0026	CUMI0035	0.051333	0.864476	0.288956	FS
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0026	CUMI0034	0.223983	0.37644	0.124543	HS
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0047	CUMI0132	0.278182	0.365129	0.099457	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0028	CUMI0030	0.27067	0.322465	0.094952	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0027	CUMI0034	0.293448	0.372874	0.094135	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0045	CUMI0127	0.286614	0.308431	0.086119	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0026	CUMI0028	0.301284	0.342755	0.086094	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0029	CUMI0030	0.288429	0.307453	0.08524	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0048	CUMI0050	0.291692	0.306017	0.083723	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0048	CUMI0178	0.304995	0.304782	0.078378	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0045	CUMI0132	0.314776	0.328028	0.078257	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0030	CUMI0034	0.292129	0.27737	0.078248	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0034	CUMI0035	0.322247	0.340165	0.076991	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0045	CUMI0130	0.32908	0.309627	0.069754	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0106	CUMI0108	0.326236	0.301656	0.069661	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0106	CUMI0111	0.325182	0.29718	0.069375	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0044	CUMI0045	0.330361	0.301885	0.068098	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0028	CUMI0035	0.348435	0.334059	0.065259	C1
<i>C. minimus</i>	CUMI0048	CUMI0051	0.335262	0.285186	0.063713	C1

Table S4. We utilized a sites-based filtering approach involving estimating multiple independent genomic site filters and intersecting these to generate a final list of usable sites. For each species the number of base pairs passing each filter, and the percent of the whole genome this corresponds to, is given. The final utilized sites list ('Combined') is the intersection of filters removing scaffolds < 1Mb in length, sex-linked and mitochondrial scaffolds, repeat regions, and regions of extreme high and low global depth.

Filter	<i>Aglais urticae</i>		<i>Aglais io</i>		<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>		<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>		<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>		<i>Cupido minimus</i>	
	Filtered bp	Filtered %	Filtered bp	Filtered %	Filtered bp	Filtered %	Filtered bp	Filtered %	Filtered bp	Filtered %	Filtered bp	Filtered %
Total genome	392818832	100.00	384156914	100.00	359616706	100.00	408152524	100.00	481009896	100.00	445890350	100.00
Scaffolds<1000000bp	392717361	99.97	383822689	99.91	355340924	98.81	405052359	99.24	480760537	99.95	445209043	99.85
Autosomes	362515041	92.29	366611579	95.43	334271162	92.95	390597629	95.70	455358909	94.67	383085145	85.91
Repeats	241128647	61.38	235176580	61.22	184300932	51.25	194051242	47.54	243716486	50.67	214427385	48.09
Depth	294054495	74.86	322276278	83.89	233707337	64.99	316107143	77.45	105494282	21.93	171917836	38.56
Combined	212590470	54.12	213246788	55.51	153753065	42.75	167120764	40.95	95163889	19.78	134923943	30.26

Filter	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>		<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>		<i>Maniola jurtina</i>		<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>		<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	
	Filtered bp	Filtered %	Filtered bp	Filtered %	Filtered bp	Filtered %	Filtered bp	Filtered %	Filtered bp	Filtered %
Total genome	441519306	100.00	420484551	100.00	402038846	100.00	379686204	100.00	511758028	100.00
Scaffolds<1000000bp	441467852	99.99	420468287	100.00	402000231	99.99	379583688	99.97	511184185	99.89
Autosomes	416794061	94.40	399930495	95.11	377448382	93.88	343360501	90.43	472204672	92.27
Repeats	205346149	46.51	239694932	57.00	203017135	50.50	242889077	63.97	214722289	41.96
Depth	340546062	77.13	310056498	73.74	276868061	68.87	283871033	74.76	319354575	62.40
Combined	179250005	40.60	204906880	48.73	171978172	42.78	211867580	55.80	177152960	34.62

Table S5. Convergence summary of the admixture analyses. For each species, we estimated admixture proportions for 1-4 clusters (K). For each K, we performed up to 100 replicates, considering the replicates to have converged if the top three replicates had a log-likelihood difference of less than 2. The best fitting number of clusters was chosen as the highest for which the runs converged within 100 replicates, and are highlighted for each species in bold.

Species	K	Replicates to convergence (max 100)	Δ log-likelihood of top 3 replicates
<i>Aglais urticae</i>	1	20	0
<i>Aglais urticae</i>	2	100	842.360509
<i>Aglais urticae</i>	3	100	494.751563
<i>Aglais urticae</i>	4	100	6652.238557
<i>Aglais io</i>	1	20	0
<i>Aglais io</i>	2	100	581.325653
<i>Aglais io</i>	3	100	1474.71087
<i>Aglais io</i>	4	100	2270.181402
<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	1	20	0
<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	2	100	1163.70081
<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	3	100	674.966235
<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	4	100	932.356258
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	1	20	0
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	2	89	0.003769
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	3	100	5540.92464
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	4	100	5159.052126
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	1	20	0
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	2	94	0.001153
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	3	100	111.892495
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	4	100	109.021803
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	1	20	0
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	2	20	6.47E-03
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	3	20	1.46E-03
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	4	20	1.80001E-05
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	1	20	0
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	2	20	2.00E-06
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	3	100	1342.053293
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	4	100	951.128209
<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	1	20	0
<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	2	100	1559.25196
<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	3	100	2563.113362
<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	4	100	1518.309168
<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	1	20	0
<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	2	100	490.08077
<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	3	100	2368.293324
<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	4	100	1948.788534
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	1	20	0
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	2	100	2583.115602
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	3	100	1736.495402
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	4	100	1458.230573
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	1	20	0
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	2	100	1372.327214
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	3	100	739.585746
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	4	100	11528.19332

Table S6. Genome wide pairwise population F_{ST} estimates for all species. We estimated F_{ST} treating individuals sampled within 15km of each other as a single population, unless indicated otherwise in the admixture analysis. If individuals showed further genetic substructure, we used the genetic clusters from the admixture analysis instead. This ensures F_{ST} was always estimated between the three regions of the study area, to provide estimates of F_{ST} at the same geographic scales across species. Estimates of Weighted F_{ST} are utilized for the manuscript, with unweighted estimates also reported here. Estimates below 0 are a product of the estimation method and should be treated as 0, and have been set to such for analyses and figures in the main text, but are left in their original state here for reference.

Species	Population 1	Population 2	Unweighted F_{ST}	Weighted F_{ST}
<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Revinge (CE)	Southeast	-0.000106	0.000079
<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Revinge (CE)	Falsterbo (SW)	0.001705	0.003925
<i>Aglais urticae</i>	Southeast	Falsterbo (SW)	0.001513	0.00332
<i>Aglais io</i>	Tvedora (CE)	Southwest	-0.000093	-0.002997
<i>Aglais io</i>	Tvedora (CE)	Backakra (SE)	0.000023	-0.003758
<i>Aglais io</i>	Backakra (SE)	Southwest	0.000075	-0.001962
<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	Revinge (CE)	Ystad Golfklubb (SE)	0.0004	0.006749
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Falsterbo (SW)	Tvedora (CE)	0.000615	0.008362
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Falsterbo (SW)	Smedstorp (SE)	0.000731	0.014402
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i>	Smedstorp (SE)	Tvedora (CE)	-0.000029	-0.005306
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Backakra (SE)	Falsterbo (SW)	0.002204	-0.01772
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Tvedora (CE)	Backakra (SE)	-0.005086	-0.083147
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	Tvedora (CE)	Falsterbo (SW)	-0.004296	-0.095952
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Tvedora (CE)	Smygehuk (SW)	0.003686	0.076287
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Tvedora (CE)	Railyard (SW)	0.003837	0.05075
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Tvedora (CE)	Smedstorp (SE)	0.002356	0.023814
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Railyard (SW)	Smygehuk (SW)	0.004456	0.070293
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Smedstorp (SE)	Smygehuk (SW)	0.004623	0.082876
<i>Cupido minimus</i>	Smedstorp (SE)	Railyard (SW)	0.004302	0.052742
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	Silvakra (CE)	Kaseberga (SE)	0.002872	0.100402
<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Tvedora (CE)	Ales Stenar (SE)	-0.000337	-0.005013
<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Tvedora (CE)	Falsterbo (SW)	-0.000919	-0.02153
<i>Lycaena phlaes</i>	Ales Stenar (SE)	Falsterbo (SW)	-0.000282	-0.010485
<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Southeast	Railyard (SW)	0.000015	-0.002712
<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Tvedora (CE)	Southeast	0.000101	-0.001154
<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	Tvedora (CE)	Railyard (SW)	0.000488	-0.004694
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Revinge (CE)	Smedstorp (SE)	-0.000681	-0.009598
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Revinge (CE)	Falsterbo (SW)	0.000935	0.008847
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	Smedstorp (SE)	Falsterbo (SW)	-0.001163	-0.00889
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Falsterbo (SW)	Tvedora (CE)	0.000273	0.003856
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Backakra (SE)	Tvedora (CE)	0.000278	0.002976
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	Backakra (SE)	Falsterbo (SW)	-0.000091	-0.001071

SI References

- Bisschop, G., Ebdon, S., Lohse, K., Vila, R., Darwin Tree of Life Barcoding collective, Wellcome Sanger Institute Tree of Life programme, Wellcome Sanger Institute Scientific Operations: DNA Pipelines collective, Tree of Life Core Informatics collective, Darwin Tree of Life Consortium, 2021. The genome sequence of the small tortoiseshell butterfly, *Aglais urticae* (Linnaeus, 1758) [version 1; peer review: 1 approved, 1 approved with reservations]. Wellcome Open Research 6. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.17197.1>
- Ebdon, S., Bisschop, G., Lohse, K., Saccheri, I., Davies, J., Wellcome Sanger Institute Tree of Life programme, Wellcome Sanger Institute Scientific Operations: DNA Pipelines collective, Tree of Life Core Informatics collective, Darwin Tree of Life Consortium, 2022. The genome sequence of the orange-tip butterfly, *Anthocharis cardamines* (Linnaeus, 1758) [version 1; peer review: 2 approved]. Wellcome Open Research 7. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.18117.1>
- Garcia-Erill, G., Albrechtsen, A., 2020. Evaluation of model fit of inferred admixture proportions. *Molecular Ecology Resources* 20, 936–949. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.13171>
- Lohse, K., Hayward, A., Laetsch, D., Marques, V., Vila, R., Tyler-Smith, C., Wellcome Sanger Institute Tree of Life programme, Wellcome Sanger Institute Scientific Operations: DNA Pipelines collective, Tree of Life Core Informatics collective, Darwin Tree of Life Consortium, 2023a. The genome sequence of the Mazarine Blue, *Cyaniris semiargus* (Rottemburg, 1775) [version 1; peer review: 2 approved]. Wellcome Open Research 8. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.19362.1>
- Lohse, K., Hayward, A., Vila, R., Wellcome Sanger Institute Tree of Life programme, Wellcome Sanger Institute Scientific Operations: DNA Pipelines collective, Tree of Life Core Informatics collective, Carvalho, A., Kawahara, A., Darwin Tree of Life Consortium, 2023b. The genome sequence of the Large Skipper, *Ochlodes sylvanus*, (Esper, 1777) [version 1; peer review: 3 approved]. Wellcome Open Research 8. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.18788.1>
- Lohse, K., Laetsch, D., Vila, R., Darwin Tree of Life Barcoding collective, Wellcome Sanger Institute Tree of Life programme, Wellcome Sanger Institute Scientific Operations: DNA Pipelines collective, Tree of Life Core Informatics collective, Darwin Tree of Life Consortium, 2021a. The genome sequence of the small copper, *Lycaena phlaeas* (Linnaeus, 1760) [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]. Wellcome Open Research 6. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.17289.1>
- Lohse, K., Mackintosh, A., Vila, R., Darwin Tree of Life Barcoding collective, Wellcome Sanger Institute Tree of Life programme, Wellcome Sanger Institute Scientific Operations: DNA Pipelines collective, Tree of Life Core Informatics collective, Darwin Tree of Life Consortium, 2021b. The genome sequence of the European peacock butterfly, *Aglais io* (Linnaeus, 1758) [version 1; peer review: 3 approved]. Wellcome Open Research 6. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.17204.1>
- Lohse, K., Weir, J., Darwin Tree of Life Barcoding collective, Wellcome Sanger Institute Tree of Life programme, Wellcome Sanger Institute Scientific Operations: DNA

- Pipelines collective, Tree of Life Core Informatics collective, Darwin Tree of Life Consortium, 2021c. The genome sequence of the meadow brown, *Maniola jurtina* (Linnaeus, 1758) [version 1; peer review: 2 approved, 1 approved with reservations]. Wellcome Open Research 6. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.17304.1>
- Lohse, K., Wellcome Sanger Institute Tree of Life programme, Wellcome Sanger Institute Scientific Operations: DNA Pipelines collective, Tree of Life Core Informatics collective, Vila, R., Darwin Tree of Life Consortium, 2023c. The genome sequence of the Common Blue, *Polyommatus icarus* (Rottemburg, 1775) [version 1; peer review: 1 approved]. Wellcome Open Research 8. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.18772.1>
- Mead, D., Saccheri, I., Yung, C., Lohse, K., Lohse, C., Ashmole, P., Smith, M., Corton, C., Oliver, K., Skelton, J., Betteridge, E., Quail, M., Dolucan, J., McCarthy, S., Howe, K., Wood, J., Torrance, J., Tracey, A., Whiteford, S., Challis, R., Durbin, R., Blaxter, M., 2021. The genome sequence of the ringlet, *Aphantopus hyperantus* Linnaeus 1758 [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]. Wellcome Open Research 6. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.16983.1>
- Santiago, E., Novo, I., Pardiñas, A.F., Saura, M., Wang, J., Caballero, A., 2020. Recent Demographic History Inferred by High-Resolution Analysis of Linkage Disequilibrium. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 37, 3642–3653. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msaa169>